

Rice & the environment

Progress in breeding semidwarf rices that are sensitive to photoperiod

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Numerous semidwarf varieties that are insensitive to photoperiod have been developed and released throughout the world. In Thailand, a series of locally developed high-yielding varieties (all insensitive) have been well accepted by farmers in areas under good irrigation in the dry season. But at least 80 percent of the riceland is planted under rainfed conditions in the monsoon season. Most of these areas are planted to tall traditional varieties that are sensitive to photoperiod. Thai scientists have sought to combine the semidwarf and intermediate plant types with sensitivity to photoperiod, as well as with elongation ability for semideep water. This might

encourage wider use of the semidwarfs and increase yields in unirrigated areas.

Selection began in 1970 from the crosses Niaw San Pah Tawng²/IR262 and Puang Nahk 16/Pankhari//C4-63. Both Niaw San Pah Tawng and Puang Nahk 16 are strongly sensitive to photoperiod in Thailand. Some of these new photoperiod-sensitive lines were first tested for yield in a preliminary trial in 1974. They were subsequently entered in multilocal yield tests in the 1975 wet season (see table). The fertilizer response of two new photoperiod-sensitive hybrid lines is compared with that of the traditional, tall, waxy Niaw San Pah Tawng and the nonwaxy Leuang Pratew 123 at four locations (see figure). The data, although somewhat limited, suggest that yields might be increased by transferring photoperiod-sensitive genes to semidwarf rices, and by heavy fertilization.

Nitrogen response of hybrid lines and traditional tall varieties grown at four fertilizer levels at one northern, one northeastern, and two central plains rice experiments stations (data courtesy of C. Kanareuga and rice experiment station personnel), Thailand.

Announcement — new report

George W. Robertson, P. Ag., agrometeorologist

Rice and Weather—G. W. Robertson. 1975. Technical Note No. 144 of the World Meteorological Organization, Geneva, Switzerland. 40 p.

This report briefly covers such topics as rice cultivation; growth and development; environmental requirements including water, photoperiod, temperature, solar energy, wind, and atmospheric vapor pressure; forecasting the yield of paddy rice; irrigation; climatic zonation for rice; and bioclimatic conditions in rice-producing areas of the world. A section on references and suggested reading lists more than 120 relevant articles.

Although the article was prepared as a general source of information for meteorologists, agricultural climatologists, and crop geographers, agronomists and others working more closely with rice may find useful material here.

Yield and some agronomic characters of semidwarf and intermediate-height glutinous and nonglutinous lines that are sensitive to photoperiod, and of a tall traditional variety.

Designation	Origin	Yield (t/ha)		Flowering date	Ht (cm)	Panicles (no./hill)	
		1974	1975				
		Av. Range					
<i>Glutinous (9 locations)</i>							
BKN 6801-53-3	LT/IR8//W1252///NSPT	3.5	3.0	1.6-4.9	Oct. 14	97	11
BKN 6721-11-8-3	NSPT ² /IR262	2.2	3.6	1.9-4.9	Oct. 23	134	10
BKN 6721-5-39-1(1)	NSPT ² /IR262	3.3	3.5	1.7-4.7	Oct. 17	136	10
NSPT	Niaw San Pah Tawng	3.3	2.0-4.8		Oct. 23	164	8
<i>Nonglutinous (6 locations)</i>							
BKN 6721-2-38-3	NSPT ² /IR262	3.4	4.8	3.0-5.7	Oct. 18	165	10
BKN 6819-36-3-1	PN 16/PKR//C4-63	4.1	4.8	3.1-6.6	Oct. 4	114	11
IR1060-90-2-1	Wag Wag ³ /IR8	3.5	4.1	2.1-5.2	Oct. 10	112	15
NM S-4	Nahng Mon S-4	3.5	4.2	3.5-4.9	Oct. 21	177	9